

CONCEPTUAL FORMULATION DESIGN IN AYURVEDA: EXPLORING THE ROLE
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ABSTRACT

The concept of *Young Drugs Siddhanta* forms the foundation of compound formulations in *Ayurveda*, emphasizing the synergistic and antagonistic interactions between multiple ingredients to achieve enhanced therapeutic efficacy. Unlike *Eka Mulika Dravya* (single-drug formulations), *Young Drugs* involves the thoughtful combination of two or more substances - herbal or mineral - guided by classical parameters such as *Rasa*, *Guna*, *Veerya*, *Vipaka*, and *Prabhava*. This article explores the comprehensive principles governing the formulation, including the stages of preparation (*Dravya Sangrahana*, *Samskara* and *Prayoga*) and highlights the significance of *Tridosha* and *Panchamahabhuta Siddhanta*, *Viruddha Ahara*, and the role of *Prakshepaka Dravyas* in optimizing bioavailability and palatability. Through proper understanding and systematic application of these concepts, *Young Drugs Siddhanta* underscores the holistic philosophy of *Ayurveda* - where the *Guna-Karma* of a medicine emerges from the combination of its constituents rather than their individual effects. A clear understanding of these *Siddhantas* ensures correct interpretation of *Vyadhi* condition and helps pharmaceutically as well as therapeutically in maintaining quality, safety and potency of the *Aushada*.

KEYWORDS: *Young Drugs*, Formulation, *Aushadha*, *Samskara*.**INTRODUCTION**

Ayurvedic medicines which are an integral part of the ancient Indian healing system aims at promoting health, preventing disease and restoring balance in the body. *Ayurvedic* medicines termed as *Aushadha* is defined as the *Dravya* which does *Rasadharana* (Drug that withhold *Rasa* in it) and *Osa* means '*Rasa*' which is an inherent property of a *Dravya* and judicious use of this *Rasa* imparts health.^[1]

Aushadha is classified into 2 types according to *Prayoga*.

1. *Eka Mulika Dravya* – Single drug formulations2. *Young Drugs* – Compound formulations

Eka Mulika Dravya are Single Drug dosage form whereas *Young Drugs* are the formulations prepared by the combination of two or more *Dravyas* which can be *Rasa Aushadhi* or *Kashta Aushadhi*. Single *Dravyas* are converted into formulation to increase their synergetic, antagonistic action.^[2]

To get the desired effect, the factors to be considered to formulate a *Young Drugs* are *Rasa*, *Guna*, *Veerya*,

Vipaka etc. or other basic concepts like *Samyoga*, *Rashi*, *Desha*, *Kala* etc.

These *Yougika Dravyas* / Compound Formulations has many benefits like it helps to nullify the toxic compound (if present any), it helps to reach the target site faster, due to the presence of many ingredients it acts as synergetic to each other. It also helps enhancing taste by masking distasteful drugs. One of the example being *Mahakashaya*.^[3]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Yougika Dravya Siddhanta explains the principle that when two or more *Dravyas* are combined, the resulting substance exhibits collective, modified, or entirely new properties, different from the individual components.

FACTORS CONSIDERED FOR THE PREPARATION OF YOUNGKA DRAVYA.

It can be classified into 3 stages.

1. Before Preparation
2. During Preparation

3. After Preparation

1. BEFORE PREPARATION/ PURVA KARMA (*Dravya Sangrahana*)

The preliminary steps followed before the main process of medicine preparation which includes *Dravya Sangraha*, *Samrakshana*, *Anukta Mana*, selection of equipment etc.

In this stage many factors are considered like.

- *Kala* - Time period as in time considered for collection of drugs etc.
- *Sthana* – Place of Collection of the ingredients
- *Avastha* – State of the ingredients at the time of collection and usage.
- *Samrakshana* - Preservation or storage of raw materials
- *Vidhi* – Process or procedure followed during the collection of ingredients.
- *Samskara* – *Purva Karmas* like drying, extracting *Swarasa* etc

Table No. 01: Factors considered before preparation of *Yougika Dravya*.

<i>KALA</i> ^[4]	<i>STHANA</i> ^[5]	<i>AVASTHA</i> ^[6]	<i>VIDHI</i> ^[7]	<i>SAMSKARA</i>	<i>GRAHYATVA</i>
<i>Mula</i> – <i>Sishira</i> and <i>Greeshma</i> <i>Patra</i> – <i>Varsha</i> and <i>Vasantha Rtu</i> <i>Saara</i> – <i>Hemanta</i> <i>Kanda and Ksheera</i> – <i>Sarat Rtu</i> <i>Phala and Kusuma</i> - In their respective season	<i>Ushna Virya</i> – <i>Vindhya</i> <i>Sheeta Virya</i> – <i>Himalayas</i>	<i>Purana-Guda</i> , <i>Vidanga</i> , <i>Madhu</i> Exception of duplication – <i>Guduchi</i> , <i>Kutaja</i> , <i>Vasa</i>	Early morning hours, <i>Sumana</i> , <i>Suchi</i> , <i>Pratha Kala</i> Direction – North facing	Clean, Proper ventilation Dried properly Stored in air tight container.	State of the ingredient and its <i>Guna</i> Eg- in case of <i>Mandura</i> if it is 60 yrs old it is considered <i>Adhama</i> , if it is 70 yrs old then it is <i>Madhyama</i> , whereas if it is 100 yrs old then it is <i>Sarva Shresta</i> .

2. DURING PREPARATION/ PRADHANA KARMA

It refers to the main/core process that transforms the raw materials into the final, usable medicine form. The preparation of *Ayurvedic* medicine is a meticulous and traditional process rooted in ancient knowledge. It includes various processes like *Bhavana*, *Marana* etc.

Here various factors are taken into account to ensure the utmost result during the preparation.

- a) *Samanya Vishesha*
- b) *Tridosha* and *Pancha Mahabhuta Siddhanta*
- c) Concept of *Rasa Panchaka*
- d) Concept of *Viruddha*
- e) Role of *Bhavana*
- f) *Samskara/Karana*
- g) *Kala*
- h) *Yogna*(plan)
- i) *Samyoga*
- j) Concept of *Prakshepaka Dravya*

SAMANYA VISHESHA^[8]

One of the basic concept to be considered during the selection and preparation of a formulation is *Samanya* and *Vishesha Siddhanta*. It stands for the synergetic and antagonistic effect between the drugs.

Samanya/ Synergetic Effect - Interaction b/w 2 or more drugs that causes the total result of the drugs to be greater than the sum of the single effects of each drug.

Eg - *Amalaki Rasayana* - Here *Amalaki Churna* is given *Bhavana* with *Amalaki Swarasa* in order to increase the efficacy which in turn helps in dose reduction.

Vishesha / Antagonistic Effect - Interaction b/w 2 or more drugs that have opposite effects on the body. It may reduce the efficacy of one or more of the drugs.

Eg - In *Anandabhairava Rasa*, *Vatsanabha* is one of the major ingredients. Here along with *Vatsanabha*, *Tankana* is also an ingredient. By adding *Tankana* it helps reduce the *Teekshnata* of *Vatsanabha*.

TRIDOSHA AND PANCHA MAHABHUTA SIDDHANTA^{[9][10]}

The *Tridoshas* - *Vata*, *Pitta* and *Kapha* - are biological energies derived from the *Panchamahabhutas* (*Akasha*, *Vayu*, *Agni*, *Jala*, *Prithvi*).

Each Ingredient in a formulation is selected based on its *Panchamahabhuta* compositions and its effect on *Doshas*.

Herbs with dominant *Akasha*, *Agni* and *Vayu* are used to pacify *Kapha Dosh* and the drugs with this predominance are used in preparations of medicines used for *Kaphaja Vyadhis*. Similarly, those with *Prithvi*, *Agni*, *Jala* qualities balances *Vata Dosh* and *Vayu*, *Jala Prithvi* helps in balancing *Pitta dosha*.

Eg - In case of *Shadanga Paneeya* which has a predominance of *Laghu* and *Ruksha Guna* inturn having predominance of *Vayu*, *Akasha* and *Agni Mahabhuta* helps in depletion of *Ama* which leads in treatment of *Jwara*.

CONCEPT OF RASA PANCHAKA^[11]

The 5 key attributes of a *Dravya* help determine the therapeutic action of a substance on the body. They are *Rasa*, *Guna*, *Virya*, *Vipaka* and *Prabhava*. Each component plays a vital role in how a medicine interacts with the body and *Tridoshas*.

- **RASA** - The 6 tastes (*Shadrasa*) / essence predominant in any *Dravya*, each *Rasa* has a specific effect on *Dosha*, *Dhatu* and *Mala* influencing health and disease condition.

Table No. 02: Dosh predominance of each Rasa.

RASA	DOSHA HARA
<i>Madhura, Amla, Lavana</i>	<i>Vata</i>
<i>Madhura, Tikta, Kashaya</i>	<i>Pitta</i>
<i>Katu, Tikta, Kashaya</i>	<i>Kapha</i>

- **GUNA** - *Guna* refers to the inherent qualities of a *Dravya*.
- **VEERYA** - The potency a *Dravya* consists of, broadly classified as *Sheeta* and *Ushna* which determines the intensity and action on *Doshas*.
- **VIPAKA** - Post-digestive effect of a *Dravya* representing the final transformation after digestion. Typically categorized into *Madhura*, *Amla* and *Katu Vipaka*.
- **PRABHAVA** - Unique or specific action of a *Dravya* which cannot be solely explained by its *Rasa*, *Guna*, *Virya* and *Vipaka*.

Eg - In case of *Simhanada Guggulu* which consists of *Triphala*, *Eranda Taila*, *Gandhaka* and *Guggulu* as the main ingredients.

- ✧ *Triphala* - *Tridosha Shamaka* having *Amla*, *Kashaya*, *Katu*, *Tikta Rasa* with *Laghu Ruksha Guna*, *Madhura Vipaka* acts as *Amapachaka*.
- ✧ *Guggulu* - because of its *Rasa*, acts antagonistic to *Ama* and *Kapha*, *Ushna Veerya* of *Guggulu* doesn't vitiate *Vata* and allow *Ama* to cause *Srothoshodha*.
- ✧ *Eranda Taila* - Having *Kashaya*, *Tikta*, *Madhura Rasa*, *Snigdha*, *Guru* and *Sara Guna*, *Ushna Virya*, *Madhura Vipaka* acts as *Agnivardhaka*, *Sroto Shodaka* and *Amapachaka*.
- ✧ *Gandhaka* - *Katu*, *Tikta rasa*, *Laghu*, *Snigdha*, *Sara Guna*, *Ushna Virya* and *Katu Vipaka* acts as *Vata-Kaphahara*, *Amapachaka* and *Shotahara*.

All these suggests that *Simhanada Guggulu* has properties such as *Amapachana*, *Virechana Karma*, *Vata- Kaphahara*, *Shothahara* and *Lekhana* which makes it highly effective in treating *Amavata*.

CONCEPT OF VIRUDDHA^[12]

The concept of *Viruddha* in *Ayurveda* refers to 'Incompatibility'. When certain *Dravyas* or substances though individually wholesome, becomes harmful when combines, processed or consumed in specific conditions. Examples for different types of *Viruddha*.

- ✧ *Desha Viruddha* - Intake of *Snigdha* and *Sheeta Ahara* in *Anupa Desha*.
- ✧ *Kala Viruddha* - Intake of *Katu* and *Ushna Ahara* in *Greeshma Rtu*.
- ✧ *Agni Viruddha* - Intake of *Laghu* and *Alpa Matra Ahara* in *Teeksha Agni* condition.
- ✧ *Matra Viruddha* - When honey and ghee are consumed in equal proportion.
- ✧ *Satmya Viruddha* - Intake of *Madhura* and *Sheeta Ahara* by a person who is used to *Katu* and *Ushna Ahara*.
- ✧ *Samskara Viruddha* - Reheating of oil which is used once.
- ✧ *Veerya Viruddha* - When fish of *Ushna Virya* consumed with *Sheeta Virya* milk.
- ✧ *Koshta Viruddha* - Usage of strong laxatives by a *Mrdu Koshta* person
- ✧ *Parihara Viruddha* - Consuming cold items after *Ushna* and *Teekshna Ahara*.
- ✧ *Upachara Viruddha* - In take of *Sheeta Dravya* after *Snehapana*.
- ✧ *Paka Viruddha* - Intake of un-cooked or Partially cooked food items.
- ✧ *Samyoga Viruddha* - When *Amla Dravyas* are taken with milk.
- ✧ *Karma Viruddha* - Avoid selection of drugs with opposite *Gunas*. (Eg - In *Sitopaladi Churna* which consists of *Vanshalochana*, *Ela*, *Pippali* and *Twak* other than *Sitopala* which are of *Ushna Guna* and *Katu Vipaka*, *Sitopala* is added in 16 parts to reduce its *Teekshanata* and *Ati Ushanata*.)

Intake of *Viruddha Ahara* can lead to formation of *Ama/toxins*, disturb the *Doshas* and manifest diseases immediately or over time. *Ayurveda* emphasizes avoiding *Viruddha* combinations to maintain *Dosha Samatva*, *Agni Bala* and overall health.

SAMSKARA/KARANA^[13]

Samskara refers to the process of purification and transformation of *Dravyas* to enhance their potency, safety and therapeutic efficacy. These *Samskaras* helps to remove *Doshas*, induce *Guna*, *Karma* and tailor them for treating certain specific *Dosha* imbalances.

"*Guna Antaraadanam*" - It is done to incorporate special effects for the drug & to reduce the toxic effects of a drug.

Eg.

- Purification of *Parada* and *Gandhaka* is done to remove impurities and toxicity. These are used in various formulations like *Rasa Parpati*, *Arogyavardhini Vati*, *Pratapalankeshwara Rasa* etc.
- *Ghrita* without *Samskara* it is *Guru*, *Agni Deepana*, *Vata-Pitta hara*. Whereas with *Samskara* usage of *Ghrita*

can be of great results. eg - *Satadouta Ghrita*, *Shatphala Gritha*.

Table No 03: Types and examples for Samskaras.

SAMSKARA	EXAMPLE
<i>Jala Samskara</i>	<i>Rakta Shali</i> after soaking in water and frying on fire becomes <i>Laja</i> (<i>Guru</i> to <i>Laghu</i>)
<i>Agni Samskara</i>	<i>Tandula</i> (<i>Guru Guna</i> to <i>Laghu Guna</i>)
<i>Shaucha Samskara</i>	Removes dirt and foreign bodies from drugs. Washing of <i>Shatavari</i> root removes mud and dirt.
<i>Manthana Samskara</i>	<i>Dadhi</i> (<i>Shothakara</i>) Turns To <i>Takra</i> (<i>Shothohara</i>)
<i>Desha Samskara</i>	In <i>Amalaki Avaleha/Amalaki Ghrita</i> - <i>Amalaki</i> to be kept for 6 days in <i>Bhasma Rashi</i> which turns as <i>Rasayana</i> .
<i>Kala Prakarsha</i>	In case of <i>Asava</i> and <i>Arista</i> it becomes fermented after 15 or more days
<i>Bhajana Samskara</i>	<i>Gritha Lepana</i> in <i>Mrt Patra</i> helps in closing of pores which reduces the chances of fungal infestation.
<i>Vasana Samskara</i>	Drugs like <i>Utpala</i> kept in water for <i>Sugandhakara</i>
<i>Bhavana Samskara</i>	<i>Amalaki Rasayana</i> - Here <i>Amalaki Churna</i> is given <i>Bhavana</i> with <i>Amalaki Swarasa</i> in order to increase the efficacy which in turn helps in dose reduction (helpful in <i>Shodhana</i> and <i>Gunavardhana</i>).

KALA^[14]

Kala refers to the time factor which is considered for preparation of any formulation.

Eg -

- In *Sneha Kalpana*, the time of preparation varies according to the *Drava-Dravya* added in the formulation. Like If milk is added then 2 days of *Paka* is done, If *Swarasa*, 3 days of *Paka* etc.
- In preparation of *Hima Kalpana*, It has to be soaked overnight/Ahoratra.
- In *Lauhadi Rasayana*, *Sthapana* is done for 1 year (12 months) with monthly *Alodana* by adding *Amalaki Swarasa* and *Madhu*.
- 3 days of *Bhavana* is done in preparation of *Sameera Pannaga Rasa*.

YOJANA (PLAN)

Yojana Refers to the thoughtful and purposeful combination/ Planning of individual *Dravyas* to create a compound formulation. It plays a crucial role in ensuring synergy and safety of the formulation. It also helps remove bad effects and provides desirable effects needed.

Eg.

- While using *Trivruth*, *Shunti* is used to remove the tenesmus produced by *Trivruth*.
- *Druthi Kalpana* – to be stored in *Kusuma Taila* (for longer shelf life)
- *Gokshura* – acts as *Sthambaka* in *Dugda Arka*

SAMYOGA^[15]

Samyoga is the permutations and combinations done to form a *Yougika Dravya*. It refers to the actual mixing or joining of the ingredients. It is the physical or chemical

union of *Dravyas* which can result in new or combined effect which might not be achieved in individual *Dravyas*.

It helps to produce quick action of drug.

Eg -

- To act as a catalyst- ie, *Parada* can be used in various forms like
 - 1) Basic ore form – *Hingula* in *Ananda Bhairava Rasa*
 - 2) *Kajjali* - in *Kharaliya Rasayanas*
 - 3) *Bhasma* form - in *Kupipakwa Rasayanas*
- To produce desirable taste - *Avipathikara* is added with *Sharkara*
- To produce a good aroma (*Vasana Samskara*) - *Ela*, *Karpura* etc are added in *Gandha Paka* in *Taila* preparation.
- To produce Synergetic effect - To increase emetic effects of *Madanaphala*, *Jimutaka Swarasa* is used as a *Bhavana Dravya*.

PRAKSHEPAKA DRAVYA

The ingredients added to preparations like *Avaleha*, *Asava*, *Arishta* etc. apart from main Ingredients are *Prakshepaka Dravyas*.

- They affirm and augment the absorption of the drug by their bio enhancing property, act as a preservative.
- Added in a minor Quantity
- Distinct to each *Kalpana*
- Act as a synergize and also aid to Pharmacological action, bestows palatability & aroma.
- The selection and quantity depend upon physicians *Yukti*.
- Eg - Honey, Jaggery, Rock Salt, Sugar, Cumin Seed Etc

- Examples: *Trikatu choorna* is used in most *Avaleha* as *Avalehas* are heavy for digestion. Property of *Trikatu* is antagonistic to *Guru and Manda* property of *Avaleha* which helps improve bioavailability and easy digestion.

3. PASHCHAT KARMA (Administration of a Formulation)

After understanding the *Yougika Dravya Siddhanta*, the formulation is administered considering *Deha, Prakriti, Agnibala, Dosha* and *Rogavastha* to ensure precise therapeutic action. The *Anupana, Matra, Kala* etc are selected to optimize proper *Grahana* and enhance the integrated *Karma* of the *Yougika Dravyas*.

CONCEPT OF ANUPANA/ SAHAPANA^[16]

Anupana is usually an adjuvant or the fluid vehicle for internal administration of medicaments whereas the word *Sahapana* is also used to the drink taken along with the medicine.

Eg.

Table No 04. Different Anupanas used for different conditions in same formulation.

Formulation	Condition	Anupana Used
<i>Narayana Churna</i>	<i>Ajirna</i>	<i>Ushna Jala</i>
	<i>Anaha</i>	<i>Sura</i>
<i>Agni Kumara Rasa</i>	<i>Kaphaja Jwara</i>	<i>Ardraka Swarasa</i>
	<i>Agni Mandhya</i>	<i>Lavanga Kashaya</i>
<i>Rasa Sindhura</i>	<i>Jirna Jwara</i>	<i>Kwatha of Guduchi + Parpata + Dhanyaka</i>
	<i>Arshas</i>	<i>Kwatha of Bala Haritaki</i>

CONCEPT OF AUSHADA SEVANA KALA^[17]

Proper *Sevana Kala* facilitates optimum absorption, directs the drug to its specific site of action, and minimizes untoward effects. It also aids in maintaining *Agni Samya* and enhances *Aushadha Bala*.

Eg:

- In case of *Gritha* administration, it is usually given during the morning hours in empty stomach. It is to ensure the complete absorption and proper digestion without formation of *Ama*.
- *Sitopaladi Churna* is given *Muhurmuhur* to avoid the accumulation of *Kapha* in *Pranavaha Srotas* and to break its *Samprapti*.

MATRA^[18]

The precise practical *Matra* can be decided only after considering the factors like *Agni, Bala, Vaya, Prakriti* and *Dosha* of the person along with the *Kala* and *Desha*. *Acharyas* have mentioned the General *Aushadha Matra* for each *Aushadha Kalpana*. Whereas the final dosage should be decided considering the above-mentioned factors according to the *Yukti* of the *Vaidya*.

Eg

Swarasa - Half *Pala* (24 ml)
Churna - 1 *Karsha* (12gm)
Rasakriya - 1 *Pala* (48ml)

The term '*Anu*' means after or alongside and the term '*Sakam*' means added with.

Eg - *Ushana Jala, Madhu, Ghrita, Takra, Ksheera* etc. According to *Sushruta - Indrajala* (Rain water) is considered as *Shresta Anupana*.

Benefits of *Anupana*

- Potency of medicine is enhanced
- Carries medicine to the target site.
- Impart flavor and Palatability.
- Have *Yogavahi Guna*.
- Helps in absorption and assimilation of medicine
- Counteract *Teekshnata, Kashayata* etc.

Different *Anupanas* are mentioned for the same formulation in different disease conditions.

This ensures proper disintegration, boost therapeutic effect needed.

Avaleha - 1 *Pala* (48gm)

DISCUSSION

- ✧ Safety, Efficacy, Stability and Palatability are the four basic requirements of a good drug dosage form
- ✧ The pharmaceutical procedures for any drug involve various steps starting from identification & collection of authentic raw material, application of standardized processing, techniques & production of quality drug, to packaging & storage of finished drug.
- ✧ It emphasizes that the overall efficacy of a formulation depends not merely on the individual properties of its ingredients, but on the synergistic interactions arising from their combination. This is reflected in the verse "*Samyoga Samyukta Dravya Guna Karmayogam*", which implies that the therapeutic potential of a compound formulation is the resultant of the collective properties of all the ingredients and their mutual interactions.
- ✧ The concept of *Samskara* is particularly significant, as it modifies the inherent properties of a drug to make it more therapeutically effective and less toxic. For example, purification of *Parada* and *Gandhaka* not only removes impurities but also imparts new therapeutic properties that make them suitable for use in *Rasa Rasayanas*. Similarly, *Bhavana*

enhances bioavailability and facilitates assimilation, as seen in *Amalaki Rasayana*.

- ◇ *Anupanas* such as *Madhu*, *Ghritha*, *Takra*, or *Ushna Jala* serve as *Yogavahi*, improving the potency and direction of drug action. The *Aushadha Sevana Kala* ensures the formulation acts in harmony with the body's physiological rhythm, maximizing efficacy and minimizing side effects.

CONCLUSION

Every concept in *Ayurveda*, have proven to have its own importance and clinical implementation. *Samyoga* is one such unique contribution of *Ayurveda* implemented in the context of *Aushadha Samyoga* which explains the preparation of *Yougika Dravyas*. *Yougika Dravya Siddhanta* emphasizes that the therapeutic potency of a formulation arises not merely from the sum of its ingredients, but from their synergistic interaction.

Yougika Dravya Siddhanta allows physician to design medicines tailored for complex clinical conditions where a single drug may be insufficient. Thus, ensuring multi-dimensional action.

Beyond nomenclature, these formulations highlight the importance of systemic stages of preparation like *Shodhana*, *Marana* etc. as each stage plays a crucial role in detoxification, potentiation etc.

A clear understanding of these *Siddhantas* ensures correct interpretation of *Vyadhi* condition and helps in prescribing the perfect *Aushadi* for that particular condition. The *Chikitsasiddhi* completely depends upon the proper use of polyherbal formulation by a *Yuktigna Vaidya*.

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